

REVIEW OPEN ACCESS

Selective Oxidation Strategies for Cost-Efficient Green Hydrogen Production via Hybrid Water Electrolysis

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable hydrogen production is essential for decarbonizing energy and chemical manufacturing; however, conventional water electrolysis is limited by the high thermodynamic and kinetic demands of the oxygen evolution reaction (OER). Hybrid water electrolysis addresses this challenge by replacing the OER with more favorable organic oxidation reactions (OORs), reducing energy input while valorizing or remediating abundant biomass- and waste-derived feedstocks. This review presents the first unified assessment that integrates techno-economic analysis with mechanistic insight and electrocatalyst design principles to identify the most viable OOR pathways. We evaluate key substrates, including glycerol, 5-hydroxymethylfurfural, urea, methanol, and ethanol, and summarize advances in noble and non-noble metal catalysts enabling selective partial oxidation at reduced voltages. The remaining challenges in catalyst stability, product separation, membrane durability, and system integration are critically examined. Overall, this review provides a comprehensive framework for guiding the development and industrial deployment of hybrid electrolyzers for low-carbon, value-added hydrogen production.

1 | Introduction

Modern society's dependence on fossil fuels for energy production continues to drive the climate crisis, one of the most pressing challenges of our time [1]. This reliance also extends to energy-intensive industrial processes such as ammonia and methanol synthesis, where fossil-derived feedstocks remain critical due to the lack of scalable, low-carbon alternatives. A transition to renewable energy is essential; however, its inherent intermittency still constrains large-scale deployment. The challenge is therefore twofold: (i) to decarbonize the vast industrial demand for fossil-derived feedstocks and (ii) to

develop scalable storage solutions that stabilize renewable electricity supply.

Hydrogen is uniquely positioned to address both challenges. In 2024, global hydrogen production reached nearly 100 million tons, of which less than 1% originated from low-emission sources [2]. The remainder was derived from fossil fuels, consuming approximately 290 billion m³ of natural gas and 90 million tons of coal equivalent. Current demand remains concentrated in established industrial applications such as petroleum refining, ammonia production, and methanol synthesis. Industrial hydrogen use is projected to grow, with

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ammonia providing a representative example: global demand is expected to double by 2050 from around 185 million tons in 2020, driven not only by fertilizer production but also by emerging applications in the chemical and energy sectors [3]. This trajectory underscores the urgent need to decarbonize hydrogen production.

To meet the growing demand for low-carbon hydrogen, large-scale deployment of renewable power is required. However, the variability of renewable sources such as wind and solar often causes grid imbalance. Electrochemical storage cells, such as lithium-ion batteries, can offer short-term buffering but face scalability limits due to material constraints and socio-environmental concerns [4]. In addition, lithium-ion batteries remain expensive to manufacture and lack the charge capacity needed for grid-scale storage ($> 200 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$) [5, 6]. Molecular hydrogen (H_2), by contrast, is an attractive energy carrier owing to its high gravimetric energy density (120 MJ kg^{-1}), which surpasses that of most fossil fuels (e.g., natural gas at 48.6 MJ kg^{-1}) [7]. Although hydrogen gas has a low volumetric energy density [8], ongoing research aims to improve its storage in inorganic hydrides [9], liquid-organic hydrogen carriers [10], and metal-organic frameworks [11]. Furthermore, decentralized hydrogen production can reduce end-user costs by minimizing large-scale distribution requirements, particularly in road transport applications [12].

Water electrolysis provides a clean and sustainable route to hydrogen production when powered by renewable electricity. Under an applied potential, water is split into hydrogen and oxygen according to the following half-cell reactions and standard potentials [13]:

Water splitting combines the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER, Equation 1) at the cathode with the oxygen evolution reaction (OER, the reverse of Equation 2) at the anode. The standard reduction potential (E^0) is related to the Gibbs energy change of a reaction under standard conditions and

can be used to estimate the thermodynamic driving force of the net redox process. Although the E^0 of the HER is 0 V_{SHE} (volts vs. the standard hydrogen electrode) by definition, the reverse OER shows a significantly higher E^0 of $1.23 \text{ V}_{\text{SHE}}$ [13, 14], making the overall water electrolysis thermodynamically endergonic. Moreover, the OER is kinetically sluggish and typically requires large overpotentials (ca. 0.40 V) due to high activation barriers, mass-transport limitations, and parasitic side reactions [15]. These factors increase the cell voltage and therefore the energy needed to drive water splitting. A further drawback is the generation of large volumes of O_2 , which has limited commercial value, poses safety risks due to its reactivity with H_2 , and can degrade electrolyzer membranes through reactive oxygen species [16]. These disadvantages are illustrated in Figure 1A.

Hybrid water electrolysis has emerged as a promising alternative in which the OER is replaced by a more thermodynamically favorable organic oxidation reaction (OOR), as shown in Figure 1B. This review presents the first comprehensive and data-driven analysis of this approach, integrating economic metrics with catalytic benchmarks to evaluate its feasibility. First, we estimate the techno-economic benefits of key OORs by comparing market prices of feedstocks and oxidation products, highlighting the importance of selective product formation. We then summarize recent advances in electrocatalyst development that have reduced operating voltages toward thermodynamic limits while maintaining high current densities. Finally, we discuss outstanding challenges in catalyst stability, product separation, and system scalability. By combining mechanistic insights with techno-economic analysis, this review provides a critical and forward-looking roadmap for translating selective OORs from laboratory demonstrations into commercially viable technologies. Although previous reviews have examined individual aspects of hybrid electrolysis [17–23], this work uniquely integrates profitability analysis, catalytic performance, design strategies, and industrial implementation considerations, offering a timely and comprehensive perspective to guide future research and development in this rapidly advancing field.

FIGURE 1 | Schematic illustrating (A) conventional water electrolysis and its disadvantages, and (B) hybrid water electrolysis and its advantages.

2 | Organic Substrates

Organic substrates for the OOR can be broadly categorized into two classes based on their fate after electrochemical oxidation: those used sacrificially and those that are valorized. Sacrificial substrates are oxidized to low-value or inert products, whereas substrates that are valorized can yield value-added chemical feedstocks after electrolysis. Strategic substrate selection, paired with controlled oxidation, can yield substantial economic benefits compared with the conventional OER. Table 1 summarizes the commonly studied substrates, possible electro-oxidation products, the minimum electrons transferred to obtain each product, substrate and product prices, recent product market revenues, the estimated profit or loss per gram of H₂ produced at the cathode, and the projected H₂ yield and OOR profit per annum. For a small number of products, prices and market revenues were unavailable owing to lack of value, production challenges, or global scarcity.

To obtain these estimates, we consider a general HER–OOR electrolysis scheme for reactant *R* producing products *P_j* and hydrogen (Equation 3). From stoichiometry and the number of electrons transferred, *n_e*, we determine the profit per gram of H₂ produced, Π_{H₂} (Equation 4). Using recent market revenues for each product, *R_{mkt}*, along with the product selling price *C_{P_j}*, we estimate the effective annual mass product, *m_{P_j}^{max}* (Equation 5). Stoichiometry then yields a projected product-market-limited annual H₂ production, assuming a unit market share, *m_{H₂}^{max}* (Equation 6). Finally, we estimate the corresponding annual hybrid electrolysis profit, Π_{yr} (Equation 7).

$$\Pi_{H_2} = \frac{2}{n_e M_{H_2}} \left[\frac{\nu_{P_j}}{\nu_R} C_{P_j} M_{P_j} - C_R M_R \right], \quad (4)$$

$$m_{P_j}^{\max} = \frac{R_{\text{mkt}}}{C_{P_j}}, \quad (5)$$

$$m_{H_2}^{\max} = m_{P_j}^{\max} \left(\frac{\nu_R}{\nu_{P_j}} \right) \left(\frac{n_e}{2} \right) \left(\frac{M_{H_2}}{M_{P_j}} \right), \quad (6)$$

$$\Pi_{\text{yr}} = R_{\text{mkt}} \left[1 - \frac{\nu_R}{\nu_{P_j}} \left(\frac{C_R}{C_{P_j}} \right) \left(\frac{M_R}{M_{P_j}} \right) \right], \quad (7)$$

where ν_R and ν_{P_j} are the stoichiometric coefficients of reactant *R* and product *P_j*, respectively; *M_R*, *M_{P_j}*, and *M_{H₂}* are the molar masses of *R*, *P_j*, and H₂, respectively; and *C_R* is the reactant selling price.

In this analysis, we account for profit from only one product at a time (e.g., glycerol can yield multiple products in a single electrolysis, but separation costs would increase). We assume constant market revenue since the reporting year, although many products show substantial projected growth. We also assume 100% selectivity and Faradaic efficiency toward the desired product and omit separation, electricity, and overhead costs due to their variability. Thus, these estimates represent an upper bound for profit and production. We intentionally keep

the model simple to provide a rapid, first-pass screen of promising OOR pathways for more detailed follow-up research.

Overall, these results underscore the importance of selectivity control, as overoxidation can severely diminish economic returns. For example, oxidation of glycerol to formic acid (four electrons) results in a net loss of €0.12 per gram of H₂, whereas selective two-electron oxidation to glyceraldehyde yields a profit of €7590.62 per gram of H₂ based solely on the reactant-product price differential. Similarly, overoxidation of methanol and ethanol to CO₂ is unprofitable, whereas partial oxidations to formic acid, formaldehyde, acetic acid, acetaldehyde, or ethyl acetate are economically favorable.

However, market price alone is insufficient to correctly predict process profitability, as this depends heavily on the market demand for a chosen product. Taking a recent market revenue of each product as an estimate for the market size, the most lucrative processes (largest Π_{yr} per substrate in Table 1) are glycerol to glyceraldehyde, lactic acid, oxalic acid, or acetic acid; 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) to 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid (FDCA); methanol to formaldehyde; and ethanol to acetic acid or ethyl acetate. These conversions also show relatively high *m_{H₂}^{max}* compared to alternative products, offering a twofold advantage.

We highlight that, in these cases, the relative amount of H₂ produced is less important for selecting an OOR process than the projected profit, as the total of the *m_{H₂}^{max}* column in Table 1 (the maximum theoretical product-market-limited annual H₂ production via hybrid electrolysis) sums to only 0.001% of the global hydrogen production in 2024 [2]. Although this fraction is small, many of the highlighted products have projected compound annual growth rates of 7%–9% between 2024 and 2034 [36, 38, 56], suggesting significant headroom for scale-up. Moreover, hybrid routes are not expected to replace all incumbent H₂ production but to contribute as one of several pathways to lower carbon hydrogen [79].

Among the most promising substrates listed in Table 1 are glycerol and HMF. Their oxidation affords substantial projected H₂ output and high-value chemicals (e.g., glyceraldehyde, acetic acid, and FDCA) used in applications from leather tanning to polymer synthesis [80, 81]. Notably, their *E⁰* values from desirable products are substantially lower than that of the OER (Equations 2, 8, 9) [79, 82], implying that the applied potentials required for the corresponding oxidations (i.e., the reverse reactions) can be considerably lower than that for the OER, reducing the energy input for concurrent HER at the cathode.

In contrast, urea is a sacrificial substrate that is oxidized to nitrogen, carbon dioxide, and water. Although it does not yield value-added products, urea oxidation offers environmental benefits such as removal of urea from wastewater and mitigation of its conversion into harmful nitrogenous by-products [83]. Moreover, its *E⁰* from nitrogen, water, and carbon dioxide

TABLE 1 | Organic substrates and possible electro-oxidation products. Prices are minimum bulk-order rates from Sigma-Aldrich (www.sigmaaldrich.com) or Fisher Scientific (www.fishersci.com), January 2025.

Electrolysis product (purity) ^a	Structure	n_e [e ⁻ /mol substrate]	C_P [€/g] ^b	Π_{H_2} [€/g H ₂]	R_{mkt} [€/year] (year) ^c	$m_{H_2}^{max}$ [tons/year]	Π_{yr} [€/year]	References
Glycerol (≥995%, €0.18 g⁻¹) [24]								
D,L-glyceraldehyde (≥90%)		2	170.40	7590.62	34,000.00 (D-, 2025)	4.47	33,963.28	[25–27]
Dihydroxyacetone (≥98%)		2	1.42	55.12	26.35 (2025)	0.42	22.94	[28–30]
D- or L-Glyceric acid (≥95%)		4	6290.00 (Na salt)	165,155.10	1.02 (2024)	6.18 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.02	[31–33]
Tartronic acid (≥97%)		8	8.20	119.79	N/A	N/A	N/A	[31, 34], N/A
Lactic acid (≥85%)		2	0.36	7.85	345.95 (2024)	21.55	169.12	[31, 35, 36]
Glycolic acid (≥99%)		6	1.56	16.84	41.57 (2024)	2.12	35.76	[31, 37, 38]
Glycolaldehyde (crystalline)		4	27.35 ^a	402.44	3.15 (2023)	< 0.01	3.11	[39–41]
Oxalic acid (≥99%)		10	0.94	6.74	56.58 (2024)	6.75	45.50	[31, 42, 43]
Glyoxylic acid (≥98%)		8	3.29	28.10	20.66 (2025)	0.69	19.25	[31, 44, 45]
Mesoxalic acid (≥98%)		10	15.02 (Ca salt)	173.91	N/A	N/A	N/A	[31, 46], N/A
Hydroxypyruvic acid (≥97%)		6	881.28 (Na salt)	15,130.27	N/A	N/A	N/A	[47, 48], N/A
Acetic acid (≥99.7%)		4	0.45	2.59	1850.45 (2024)	276.65	715.34	[31, 49, 50]
Formic acid (≥95%)		4	0.35	-0.12	56.70 (2024)	14.22	-1.64	[31, 51, 52]
5-hydroxymethylfurfural (99%, €22.50 g⁻¹) [53]								
2,5-furandicarboxylic acid (97 %)		6	28.00	252.98	52.77 (2024)	0.07	18.51	[54–56]
2,5-formyl-furancarboxylic acid (≥98%)		4	225.35	7111.83	N/A	N/A	N/A	[54, 57], N/A
5-hydroxymethyl-2-furancarboxylic acid (N/A)		2	93.24	5154.88	10.20 (2024)	< 0.01	8.02	[54, 58, 59]
2,5-diformylfuran (97 %)		2	166.00	8792.80	12.75 (2024)	< 0.01	10.99	[60–62]

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

Electrolysis product (purity) ^a	Structure	n_e [e ⁻ /mol substrate]	C_{P_j} [€/g] ^b	Π_{H_2} [€/g H ₂]	R_{mkt} [€/year] (year) ^c	$m_{H_2}^{max}$ [tons/year]	Π_{yr} [€/year]	References
Urea (99%, €0.53 g⁻¹) [63]								
NO _x ⁻ , nitrogen, carbon dioxide, and water		6	0.00	-5.25	N/A	N/A	N/A	[64], N/A,N/A
Methanol (≥998.%, €0.10 g⁻¹) [65]								
Formic acid (≥95%)		4	0.35	3.19	56.70 (2024)	14.22	45.43	[51, 52, 66]
Formaldehyde (36.5% – 38.0%)		2	0.15	0.64	382.50 (2024)	171.53	110.43	[67–69]
Carbon dioxide		6	0.00	-0.53	N/A	N/A	N/A	[70], N/A,N/A
Ethanol (€0.04 g⁻¹) [71]								
Acetaldehyde (99%)		2	0.81	16.75	189.55 (2024)	10.73	179.76	[72–74]
Acetic acid (≥99.7%)		4	0.45	6.23	1850.45 (2024)	276.65	1724.26	[49, 50, 72]
Ethyl acetate (≥99.5%)		2	0.12	1.70	527.85 (2024)	201.69	343.85	[75–77]
Carbon dioxide		12	0.00	-0.15	N/A	N/A	N/A	[78], N/A,N/A

^aPrice corresponds to half the price per gram of the dimeric crystal.

(Equation 10) makes the process more thermodynamically favorable than the OER [84].

Methanol and ethanol are less common OOR substrates because of their own economic value, though their partial oxidations also lead to valuable products. Still, their E^0 values from CO₂ (Equations 11 and 12) make them attractive for improving the energy efficiency of hybrid electrolysis; in practice, their partial oxidations to value-added products are of greatest interest [85].

Only the most widely studied OOR substrates are presented in Table 1, though others such as ammonia or hydrazine have been reported and reviewed [17, 86]. One recent review identifies hydrazine as particularly promising for reducing H₂ production cost relative to several candidates considered here, while also highlighting the practical potential of glycerol, HMF, urea, ethanol, and methanol if large oxidation overpotentials can be overcome [87]. Given the growing profitability of value-added products, we anticipate that glycerol, HMF, and short-

chain alcohol processes will become increasingly competitive, whereas use of urea will remain compelling on environmental grounds. Among these, glycerol and HMF have emerged as the most promising substrates for hybrid HER–OOR electrolyzers owing to their biomass-derived origins, high valorization potential, and favorable redox properties. Accordingly, they will serve as the primary focus of the following sections. Unless otherwise noted, onset potentials refer to a current density of 1.00 mA cm⁻², as this convention is a common source of confusion when comparing electrochemical systems across studies [88].

2.1 | Glycerol Oxidation

Glycerol is a renewable feedstock and major byproduct of biodiesel production, whose abundance has increased significantly in recent years due to the growing demand for biodiesel. Its electro-oxidation offers a sustainable, energy-efficient route to value-added chemicals at the anode while simultaneously producing hydrogen at the cathode (Figure 2A,B) [18, 19].

As discussed in the Introduction, hybrid water electrolysis incorporating OORs can provide substantial economic advantages over the conventional OER. For example, the E^0 of the glyceraldehyde/glycerol couple lies at 0.23 V_{SHE} (Equation 8), markedly lower than the 1.23 V_{SHE} demanded by the OER, thus reducing the theoretical electrical input required to produce green hydrogen [79].

In a pioneering study, Kim and colleagues reported the co-production of hydrogen and value-added chemicals from

FIGURE 2 | (A) Possible marketable electro-oxidation products of glycerol; the minimum electrons required to form each product are indicated. (B) Schematic of glycerol oxidation coupled with the hydrogen evolution reaction.

glycerol using a Pt/C catalyst [89]. Electrolysis at 1.12 V_{RHE} (volts vs. the reversible hydrogen electrode) in a pH 0.30 electrolyte yielded a mixture of glyceraldehyde, glyceric acid, and hydroxypyruvic acid, while enabling hydrogen evolution at significantly lower cell potentials than conventional water splitting. Their cost analysis further indicated that electrochemical production of glyceraldehyde was \$2.61 per kilogram cheaper than through traditional synthetic methods, emphasizing the dual economic incentive of using the glycerol oxidation reaction (GOR) in hybrid systems.

2.1.1 | Electrolysis Products

Glycerol can be electrochemically converted into a diverse set of C_1 – C_3 products, including dihydroxyacetone, glyceric acid, glycolic acid, and formic acid (Figure 2A) [20, 21, 90]. The first three are valuable monomers in the manufacture of polyesters and nylons [91]. Formic acid, although less profitable, is used in leather tanning and is increasingly in demand as a fuel for direct formic acid fuel cells, offering several operational benefits such as high power density, minimal fuel crossover, and simple system design [92–94]. A comprehensive economic analysis identified glyceric acid, dihydroxyacetone, and glyceraldehyde as particularly lucrative, owing to their high economic potential per gram of glycerol, in partial disagreement with Table 1, likely due to differences in market prices between that study and the present work [79].

Harnessing the full potential of the GOR is challenging because of its multi-electron mechanism. Pathway selection depends on the interplay among sequential dehydrogenation, isomerization, and C–C scission steps. Although the mechanism has not been fully elucidated for either noble or non-noble metal catalysts [90, 95], efforts to improve selectivity have focused on tailoring catalytic surface structures, designing multifunctional electrodes, and optimizing operating conditions [39, 96, 97].

Pathway branching is governed largely by the adsorption geometry of early glyceryl/carbonyl intermediates and the availability of surface-adsorbed OH. Alkaline media are

generally more favorable than acidic conditions for the GOR because adsorbed hydroxyl species improve thermodynamics and kinetics and enhance catalyst stability, though product distributions remain broad [25, 98]. Computational studies have been instrumental in clarifying these effects and guiding selectivity control. Valter and colleagues used density functional theory (DFT) calculations to probe early deprotonation steps on transition-metal (111) surfaces and Co(0001) [99]. They reported that Ru, Rh, Ir, Ag, and Au favor dihydroxyacetone formation, whereas Cu, Co, and Ni favor hydroxypyruvic acid; Pd and Pt were less selective, yielding mixtures of dihydroxyacetone and glyceraldehyde based on oxidation thermodynamics. Meng and colleagues further showed that the adsorption mode of key reaction intermediates directly influences selectivity [100]. In particular, adsorption via C tends to preserve the C_3 backbone and favor glyceric acid, whereas multidentate/O-bound modes promote C–C cleavage to C_2 / C_1 products such as formic acid. Although these studies focused on Pt(111) and Ag(111), respectively, the principles are expected to generalize to other catalysts. Consistent with this view, a recent experimental operando study linked single C adsorption on a Pt–Au alloy to high C_3 selectivity and suppressed C–C scission [101]. Together, these studies underscore the value of computational modeling in elucidating the GOR mechanism and advancing product selectivity through alloy-modulated adsorption control.

2.1.2 | Noble Metal Catalysts

Despite the above insights, the development of effective electrocatalysts for the GOR remains challenging. Noble metals and their oxides are frequently reported due to their high alcohol oxidation activity. Gomes and colleagues reported glycerol oxidation on Pt(111) under acidic conditions with an onset potential of ca. 0.50 V_{RHE} , significantly lower than that of the OER [102]. Kwon and Koper used Au electrodes to produce glycolic and formic acid with an onset near 0.90 V_{RHE} , indicating superior activity for Pt under those conditions [103].

FIGURE 3 | (A) Comparison of GOR selectivity on different Au facets measured by in situ Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. Reproduced under the terms of the CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0 license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>). Copyright 2024, The Authors, co-published by University of Science and Technology of China and American Chemical Society [104]. (B) Linear sweep voltammetry curves of various GOR/OER-HER systems using carbon nanosheets (CNs) and carbon-supported catalysts with and without glycerol (GLY) at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} . Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2022, published by Elsevier B.V [106]. Product distribution and conversion rate of GOR under (C) constant and (D) pulsed electrolysis: $0.30 V_{\text{RHE}}$ for 5 s, followed by $0.60\text{--}1.10 V_{\text{RHE}}$ for 5 s and repeat. Reproduced under the terms of the CC-BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). Copyright 2024, The Authors, published by Springer Nature [107]. FA, formate; GCA, glycolate; GLA, glycerate; LA, lactate; OA, oxalate; TA, tartronate.

Facet effects on Au have also been elucidated: the lowest onset potential occurs on Au(100) due to facile formation of surface-adsorbed OH species necessary to catalyze the oxidation; Au(111) favors C_2 products, whereas Au(100) favors C_3 products (Figure 3A) [104]. Pd shows good activity as well, with boron-doped Pd nanoparticles delivering current densities nearly eight times higher than that of commercial Pd/C at an onset potential of $0.74 V_{\text{RHE}}$ [105].

Selectivity control is crucial when deploying noble metals. As noted above, alloying Pt with Au can enforce single-C adsorption and deliver up to 95% C_3 selectivity at $0.40 V_{\text{RHE}}$, decreasing to 62% at $1.60 V_{\text{RHE}}$ with a high current density of 921 mA cm^{-2} on Pt-Au/Ni foam [101]. Additional control can be achieved via pulsed-potential electrolysis to mitigate surface poisoning and overoxidation on Pt. In situ Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy showed that pulsing increased glyceric acid selectivity from 37.8% at constant $0.70 V_{\text{RHE}}$ to 81.8% (Figure 3C,D) [107]. This material-agnostic strategy complements facet and composition tuning and can also improve resilience to impurities in crude glycerol.

Engineering metal-oxide interfaces provides another route to selectivity. For example, although carbon nanotube-supported Au shows poor selectivity for glyceric acid due to poisoning by this substrate, incorporation of CeO_2 into the support inhibits re-adsorption, limiting overoxidation and improving conversion/selectivity at $1.12 V_{\text{RHE}}$ relative to single-component supports [108]. Similarly, $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ -supported Pt improved lactic acid selectivity to 61.3%, representing nearly double that of

standalone Pt/C and the highest selectivity reviewed for this transformation, at 20 mA cm^{-2} and cell voltage $< 1.00 V_{\text{RHE}}$ [109]. Combined theoretical and experimental analyses showed that Pt sites mediate dehydrogenation, whereas $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ provides acidic sites steering lactic acid formation. These and related studies [110, 111] showcase the impressive modulation capabilities of supported noble metal-based catalysts for hybrid electrolysis.

Cost remains a limitation for noble metals, but alloying with non-noble elements can reduce precious-metal loading while retaining activity. For instance, Li and colleagues reported a bifunctional CoPt/carbon-nanosheet catalyst enabling both HER and GOR (to formate) across a wide pH range, achieving 100 mA cm^{-2} at just $1.71 V_{\text{RHE}}$, approximately 200 mV lower than conventional water splitting under the same conditions (Figure 3B) [106]. The combination of such cost reductions with previous strategies for optimizing product selectivity could make noble metal-based GOR catalysts both effective and practical.

2.1.3 | Non-Noble metal catalysts

In pursuit of economically viable alternatives, research has increasingly focused on non-noble metal catalysts, particularly nickel-based systems. Ni-based catalysts are chemically stable under the highly alkaline conditions favorable for the GOR, making them especially appealing. However, they tend to favor overoxidation to low-value formic acid rather than economically viable C_3 products, albeit at lower operating potentials. For example, Li and colleagues utilized nickel-molybdenum nitride

FIGURE 4 | (A) Linear sweep voltammetry curves of nickel–molybdenum nitride nanoplates coated on a carbon cloth anode in 1.00 M KOH with and without 0.10 M glycerol at a scan rate of 2 mV s^{-1} . Reproduced under the terms of the CC-BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). Copyright 2019, The Authors, published by Springer Nature [112]. (B) Product distribution for GOR with 25 mM glycerol after passing 18 C at $1.52 V_{\text{RHE}}$ using an amorphous $\alpha\text{-Ni(OH)}_2$ anode under various pH conditions; selectivity for DHA and FA, inset (% in white). Reproduced under the terms of the CC-BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). Copyright 2022, The Authors, published by Springer Nature [39]. (C) Selectivity and glycerol conversion (% in red) of GOR at $1.35 V_{\text{RHE}}$ at room temperature in 1.00 M KOH + 0.10 M glycerol over various catalysts after 6 h. Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2024, published by Elsevier Ltd [113]. DHA, dihydroxyacetone; FA, formate; GCA, glycolate; GCAD, glycolaldehyde; GLAD, glyceraldehyde; HPA, hydroxypyruvate; LA, lactate; OA, oxalate; TA, tartrate.

(Ni–Mo–N) nanoplates coated on carbon cloth to generate high-purity hydrogen and formate, achieving 10 mA cm^{-2} at just $1.30 V_{\text{RHE}}$ in a pH 14 electrolyte, which is 270 mV below the cell potential for the OER at the same current density (Figure 4A) [112]. This catalyst outperforms comparable Ni and IrO_2 nanoplates on carbon cloth due to its lower charge-transfer resistance, as determined from electrochemical impedance spectra.

Another study reported the activation of NiV layered double-hydroxide (LDH) electrodes for tandem HER-GOR [97]. The average oxidation state of the anodic Ni sites was increased electrochemically to favor +3 or +4, whereas plasma treatment reduced the oxidation state of cathodic Ni centers to favor +2. This regulation of the well-established $\text{Ni(OH)}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NiOOH}$ phase change boosted activity for both processes, yielding formate and hydrogen at a cell potential of just $1.25 V_{\text{RHE}}$ at 10 mA cm^{-2} in a pH 13.9 electrolyte. Together, these results illustrate how tuning the population of Ni(III/IV) sites can lower onset potentials and enhance catalytic activity, although this same shift also increases the propensity for overoxidation to formate.

Many other Ni-containing electrocatalysts have been reported to produce formate from glycerol at the anode in a pH 14 electrolyte [114–116], although one particular study stands out. Goetz and co-workers examined the effect of electrolyte pH on product distribution using an amorphous $\alpha\text{-Ni(OH)}_2$ electrode. They found that strongly alkaline conditions ($\text{pH} \geq 13$) favored a potential-dependent hydride transfer mechanism that leads to C–C bond cleavage and formic acid formation, whereas milder conditions ($\text{pH} \leq 10$) promoted an indirect hydrogen atom transfer mechanism that yields dihydroxyacetone [39]. Lowering the pH therefore improves product value but increases the oxidation onset potential by approximately 60 mV, creating a clear trade-off between energy input and selectivity. This balance suggests that the Ni-based systems discussed above could benefit from evaluation in less alkaline conditions to determine whether C_3 product formation can be enhanced without incurring prohibitive potential penalties.

Selectivity improvements have also been pursued by doping Ni with other non-noble metals or by engineering interfaces with mixed-metal oxide supports. A study on bimetallic CoNi foam

films showed that tuning the Co/Ni ratio increased the density of high-valent Ni(III/IV) oxidation centers, which are mediated by Co(III) and Co(IV), and induced indirect oxidation to dihydroxyacetone at $1.36 V_{\text{RHE}}$. This represents a 290 mV reduction compared to the OER at the same current density [96]. In a related study, Ni and NiBi nanoparticles supported on carbon favored formate production at $1.35 V_{\text{RHE}}$, whereas incorporation of $\text{Sb}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{SnO}_2$ and CeO_2 into the support shifted selectivity toward C_3 products such as glycerate and lactate by suppressing C–C bond scission (Figure 4C) [113]. Although these mixed-metal oxide supports showed higher onset potentials than the carbon-based systems, both remained ca. 280 mV lower than the OER, reaffirming the intrinsic advantage of the GOR over conventional anodic water oxidation.

2.1.4 | Reaction optimization principles

Here, we summarize key directions for future catalyst design and reaction-condition optimization for the GOR. For noble metal-based catalysts, efforts should focus on maximizing selectivity toward value-added C_3 products while reducing manufacturing cost and susceptibility to poisoning. Alloying with non-precious metals offers a promising route, and engineering metal-oxide interfaces to enforce monodentate C-adsorption with moderated binding energies may further enhance selectivity. In addition, pulsed-potential electrolysis should be explored more broadly, as periodic removal of surface poisons and restoration of adsorbed OH can improve both stability and tolerance to impurities present in crude glycerol feedstocks.

For non-noble metal catalysts, similar principles can be applied. Ni-based systems show encouraging activity, although they typically operate at higher potentials than noble metals and often promote overoxidation to low-value products. Lowering operating potentials could be approached by tuning the $\text{Ni(OH)}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NiOOH}$ equilibrium to increase the population of GOR-active Ni(III/IV) sites at more favorable potentials. As Ni(III/IV) species also drive C–C scission and formic acid formation, selectivity may be improved by introducing high-valent dopants or by supporting the catalysts on metal oxides that favor indirect oxidation pathways, mirroring strategies used for

noble metal analogues. Another important consideration is electrolyte alkalinity: most Ni-based catalysts have only been assessed under highly alkaline conditions, which lower onset potentials but bias product distributions toward C–C cleavage. We therefore propose that evaluating these systems under milder alkaline conditions may suppress overoxidation sufficiently to promote the formation of higher value C₃ products.

In summary, electrochemical GOR offers an attractive path for reducing the energy requirements of green hydrogen production. However, achieving high selectivity for value-added products at low cell potentials remains a central challenge. Successful industrial deployment will require catalysts that combine strong C₃ selectivity with low cost and operational stability across a wide range of electrolysis conditions.

2.2 | HMF Oxidation

Similar to glycerol, HMF can be derived from biomass feedstocks and is widely recognized as a promising substrate for the OOR. Its primary route of synthesis involves the processing of lignocellulose, the dominant structural component of plant cell walls and the most abundant inedible bioresource [117]. This pathway begins with the depolymerization of cellulose (constituting up to 55% of lignocellulosic biomass, depending on the source) [117] into glucose, followed by isomerization to fructose and dehydration to form HMF (Figure 5A,B) [118].

The E^0 of the valuable FDCA/HMF couple (see Table 1) is a thermodynamically advantageous 0.30 V_{SHE} (Equation 9) [82], representing a substantial decrease compared with the OER. The first demonstration of this transformation was reported by Grabowski and colleagues in 1991, who used a NiOOH electrode to achieve a 71% FDCA yield at 1.67 V_{RHE} and 16 mA cm⁻²

[119]. More recently, Cha and Choi paired cathodic hydrogen production with HMF oxidation mediated by 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine-1-oxyl (TEMPO), achieving > 90% FDCA yield at potentials as low as 0.60 V_{RHE} [120]. Together, these results establish HMF as a highly promising anodic substrate for hybrid water electrolysis, enabling hydrogen generation at reduced energy input.

2.2.1 | Electrolysis Products

The electro-oxidation products of HMF highlight its exceptional potential as an organic substrate. Complete oxidation to CO₂ is undesirable due to environmental concerns, whereas selective oxidation to FDCA or other partially oxidized intermediates offers considerable economic value. Anodic electrolysis of HMF involves oxidation of both alcohol and aldehyde moieties and proceeds through two main pathways: initial oxidation of the alcohol group to form 2,5-diformylfuran (DFF), or oxidation of the aldehyde to yield 5-hydroxymethyl-2-furancarboxylic acid (HMFCFA). These intermediates are then converted into 5-formyl-2-furancarboxylic acid (FFCA), and finally into FDCA, corresponding to the transfer of a total of six electrons (Figure 5B) [121]. Degradation of HMF to humin-like species or to maleic acid can also occur under strongly alkaline solutions [122].

Ex situ high-performance liquid chromatography analyses have shown that the dominant pathway depends on electrolyte pH and applied voltage, with the HMFCFA pathway favored under strongly alkaline conditions [123–125]. This trend aligns with the previously noted pH-dependent mechanistic switch observed for the GOR on NiOOH, where the reaction transitions between a potential-dependent and an indirect oxidation mechanism [39]. Although the underlying cause of this switch

FIGURE 5 | (A) Schematic of lignocellulosic biomass extraction. (B) HMF synthesis and electrochemical oxidation pathways.

has not yet been fully elucidated for HMF systems, this issue is less critical here because FDCA (the desired product) is accessible through either pathway. Mechanistic control is therefore primarily relevant for minimizing cell potentials and maximizing FDCA selectivity.

Beyond their role as intermediates, these oxidation products also serve as valuable platform chemicals [126]. For instance, DFF is a precursor for polymers [127], resins [128], fungicides [129], fluorescent materials [130], and pharmaceuticals [131]. HMFCFA has shown promise as an interleukin inhibitor [132] and an antitumor agent [133], and FFCA can be used in the synthesis of drug derivatives [134, 135]. Among these, FDCA stands out and has been listed by the US Department of Energy as one of the top twelve biomass-derived platform chemicals with the highest commercial potential [136, 137].

FDCA's importance is reinforced by its central role in polymer chemistry, particularly in the synthesis of polyethylene furanoate (PEF), a renewable and recyclable alternative to polyethylene terephthalate (PET) [136]. PEF offers thermal and mechanical properties comparable to those of PET (melting point: 210°C–215°C) [138] and can be processed through existing PET recycling infrastructure. Notably, PEF shows superior O₂ and CO₂ barrier properties, making it especially attractive for food and beverage packaging [138]. It is synthesized via polymerization of FDCA with ethylene glycol [139], the latter of which can be sustainably produced via glycerol hydrogenolysis [140], providing a fully biomass-based route to recyclable plastics. These attributes firmly establish FDCA as a cornerstone product in HMF valorization.

2.2.2 | Noble Metal Catalysts

As with the GOR, noble metals such as Pt, Pd, and Au have been investigated for their catalytic efficiency in HMF electro-oxidation. Despite their high intrinsic activity, their broader industrial use is constrained by manufacturing costs. Vuyuru and Strasser first reported the Pt-catalyzed electro-oxidation of HMF, obtaining only 18% DFF and trace amounts of FDCA at a current density of 0.44 mA cm⁻² in a pH 10 electrolyte (Figure 6A) [141].

More recently, the HMF oxidation activity of various Au crystal facets has been examined. Au(111) and Au(100) were found to support full oxidation to FDCA at high potentials, whereas Au(110) promoted only partial oxidation to HMFCFA. This conclusion was drawn from the absence of an HMFCFA oxidation peak in the cyclic voltammograms recorded on Au(110) compared with the other facets (Figure 6C–E) [142]. Previous supporting DFT studies of the non-electrochemical reaction indicate that C–H dehydrogenation to form HMFCFA is barrierless only on Au(110), consistent with its higher selectivity for this intermediate [143]. A more complete computational study would nevertheless be valuable for validating this facet-dependent behavior by explicitly accounting for electric double-layer effects on reaction thermodynamics and kinetics.

The potentials required for FDCA formation on Au were significantly reduced in the study of Chadderdon and colleagues, who compared the activity and selectivity of Pd/C, Au/C, and a range of bimetallic Pd–Au/C catalysts with different Pd/Au ratios. Their results showed that Au is most active for aldehyde

FIGURE 6 | (A) Conversion, yield, and selectivity of HMF electrolysis on a Pt anode at pH 10 under 1 bar N₂ at room temperature and 0.44 mA cm⁻². Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2012, published by Elsevier B.V [141]. (B) Molar yield of FDCA after 1 h electrolysis of 0.10 M KOH + 0.02 M HMF using various carbon-supported Pd–Au anodes at 0.90 V_{RHE}, room temperature. Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2014, published by The Royal Society of Chemistry [54]. Comparative cyclic voltammetry curves of (C) Au(111), (D) Au(100), and (E) Au(110) electrodes in solutions containing 3.50 mM HMF, 3.50 mM HMFCFA, and 3.50 mM FFCA in 0.10 M NaOH at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. Reproduced under the terms of the CC-BY-NC-ND license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>). Copyright 2025, The authors, published by Springer Nature [142]. OCP = open circuit potential.

oxidation (HMF to HMFCFA), whereas Pd is more active for alcohol oxidation (HMF to DFF). As both oxidation steps are essential for FDCA formation, the alloyed Pd₁Au₂/C catalyst outperformed its monometallic analogues, achieving an FDCA yield of 83% at 0.90 V_{RHE}, compared with only 11% and 1% for Pd/C and Au/C, respectively (Figure 6B) [54]. These findings highlight an alternative strategy for improving HMF electro-oxidation on Au: tailoring alloy composition rather than relying solely on crystal facet control. This demonstrates how noble metal-based catalysts can be tuned to deliver high FDCA selectivity at low operating potentials.

2.2.3 | Non-Noble Metal Catalysts

To improve the economic feasibility of HER supported by HMF electro-oxidation, a wide range of anodic non-noble metal electrocatalysts have been explored. Ni-based systems are particularly prominent due to their proven activity in aldehyde and alcohol oxidation, as discussed for the GOR. Ni is abundant, cost-effective, and stable under the alkaline conditions required for HMF oxidation. Its activity depends on the formation of Ni(III/IV) from Ni(II), which typically occurs only at relatively positive potentials (> 1.00 V_{RHE}), with both direct and indirect oxidation pathways possible, similar to the GOR [82]. As with the GOR, electrolyte pH plays a crucial role in determining product selectivity. High Faradaic efficiencies for FDCA formation are obtained at pH 14, although HMF can undergo significant degradation to undesired products under these conditions. Achieving high FDCA selectivity therefore requires balancing these competing effects. One study systematically examined this pH dependence on Ni foam, finding that maintaining the [OH⁻]:[HMF] ratio between 2 and 4 maximizes Faradaic efficiency (> 90%) at pH 13.44 and 1.52 V_{RHE}, close to the onset of the Ni(II)/Ni(III/IV) transition at 1.40 V_{RHE} [144]. When highly alkaline conditions cannot be avoided, Zhang and colleagues demonstrated an alternative strategy that helps limit HMF degradation. By using low-temperature electrolysis, they reported substantial increases in both selectivity and Faradaic efficiency toward FDCA, while also achieving higher current densities than at room temperature (Figure 7A) [145]. Interestingly, this approach also improved the kinetics of HMF

oxidation. A complementary report demonstrated the feasibility of alkaline-free HMF electro-oxidation using Ni_{0.85}Co_{0.15}(OH)₂ as a redox mediator, exploiting Co-enhanced aldehyde oxidation to achieve a 93.9% FDCA yield at 1.40 V_{RHE} [146]. Together, these studies punctuate the importance of designing reaction environments that suppress side reactions and promote efficient HMF conversion into value-added FDCA.

Although reaction selectivity remains essential, recent research has increasingly focused on improving HMF oxidation activity on Ni electrocatalysts at lower operating potentials. One strategy is to modulate the electron density of Ni sites through doping or alloying. For example, DFT studies on Mn-doped NiS nanosheets grown on 3D graphite felt revealed that Mn incorporation lowers the adsorption energy of HMF relative to undoped NiS, attributed to an upward shift in the surface *d*-band center that strengthens adsorption. This suggests that HMF adsorption may serve as a computational descriptor for catalytic activity. The doped nanosheets delivered a 97.6% FDCA yield at 500 mA cm⁻², outperforming undoped NiS and Ni(OH)₂ nanosheets, and enabled continuous-flow production of FDCA at 44.32 g h⁻¹ at 1.68 V_{RHE} [149].

A similar approach was applied to NiFe layered double hydroxide (LDH) nanosheets, widely studied for the OER but evaluated here for the first time for HMF oxidation. The results were highly promising: a 98% FDCA yield was achieved at 1.33 V_{RHE}, a potential below the OER threshold. The catalyst also showed a low onset potential (1.25 V_{RHE}) and a Tafel slope of 63.2 mV dec⁻¹, outperforming NiAl LDH, NiGa LDH, Ni(OH)₂, and unmodified carbon paper (Figure 7B). The enhanced performance was attributed to the Fe(II)/Fe(III) redox couple facilitating Ni(II)/Ni(III/IV) conversion during HMF oxidation [147]. These findings highlight the potential of adapting OER-active materials for anodic HMF electrolysis, given the mechanistic parallels involving surface OH and OOH intermediates.

Consistent with the GOR, interface engineering has also emerged as an effective route for improving HMF oxidation activity at lower cell voltages than the OER. Carbon-coupled Ni₃N nanosheets provide a representative example, achieving a 98% FDCA yield at 1.38 V_{RHE} (50 mA cm⁻²). Their improved activity relative to unsupported Ni₃N was attributed to more

FIGURE 7 | (A) Comparison of HMF conversion, FDCA yield, and Faradaic efficiency toward FDCA at room temperature and low temperature using carbon-supported Ni anodes at 1.40 V_{RHE} in 2.00 M KOH. Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2025, published by Elsevier B.V [145]. (B) Linear sweep voltammetry curves of carbon fiber paper electrodes with and without growth of NiFe LDH nanosheets in 1.00 M KOH at a scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹ in the presence and absence of 10 mM HMF. Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2018, published by American Chemical Society [147]. (C) Comparison of current densities obtained at various potentials using a hierarchical CoFe/NiFe LDH composite electrode before and after the addition of 10 mM HMF. Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2021, published by Wiley-VCH GmbH [148].

than double the electrochemical double-layer capacitance and reduced impedance, which together enhanced charge transfer and conductivity [150]. Interface engineering can also be combined with alloying, as demonstrated using a hierarchical CoFe/NiFe LDH composite. This material has Ni(III/IV) as the active sites (confirmed via operando Raman spectroscopy), whereas interfacial Fe and Co regulate valence cycling. Full conversion of HMF into FDCA was observed at 1.40 V_{RHE} (38 mA cm^{-2}) with 99.8% Faradaic efficiency, and current densities nearly doubled relative to electrolysis without HMF across a range of potentials (Figure 7C) [148]. Oxygen vacancy-rich NiCoMn LDH nanosheets have also been shown to catalyze HMF oxidation effectively by exposing additional Ni(III/IV) active sites, whose formation is mediated by the Mn(II)/Mn(III) redox couple. This system achieved a 91.7% FDCA yield at 1.50 V_{RHE} , with an onset potential lower than that of the OER [151].

2.2.4 | Reaction Optimization Principles

We now summarize our recommendations for optimizing HMF electro-oxidation to support cathodic HER, drawing on the studies reviewed above. For noble metal-based catalysts, their high cost requires strategies that maximize their performance and profit margin. Crystal facet engineering can in principle deliver exceptional selectivity, although it is labor-intensive and costly. A more practical approach is to exploit the complementary effects of alloying, where different metals improve oxidation of the aldehyde or alcohol functionalities of HMF. Tailoring alloy composition in this way can promote complete oxidation to FDCA at the lowest possible potentials.

For non-noble metal catalysts, higher operating potentials are generally required, but this drawback is offset by substantially lower material costs. Ni remains the most promising candidate, and its activity can be improved by optimizing electrolysis conditions such as pH and temperature to lower onset potentials while maintaining HMF stability. Additional reductions in cell voltage can be achieved by combining alloying with interface engineering to modulate the Ni(II) to Ni(III/IV) transition, thereby enhancing charge transfer and increasing the number of exposed active sites. Given the mechanistic similarities between HMF oxidation and the OER, adapting OER-active catalysts for anodic HMF electrolysis represents a particularly compelling direction that has already shown encouraging results.

A notable gap in current research is the limited use of computational methods to probe HMF oxidation mechanisms. As a result, catalyst development remains largely empirical, often requiring extensive laboratory screening. Existing studies suggest that HMF adsorption energy may serve as a useful catalytic activity descriptor, but its role requires more systematic investigation. Advances in this direction would support more predictive catalyst design and reduce the reliance on trial-and-error experimental screening.

Overall, electro-oxidation of HMF to FDCA represents a highly promising strategy for reducing the energy requirements of green hydrogen production. Numerous catalytic systems and reaction-optimization principles have been developed to enhance energy efficiency and selectivity toward value-added products. Moving forward, long-term catalyst stability and integration with biomass processing infrastructure will be

essential for realizing the full industrial potential of this technology.

2.3 | Urea Oxidation

Unlike glycerol and HMF, urea is a sacrificial substrate whose value in hybrid electrolysis stems primarily from its environmental significance. As a prevalent waste byproduct in industrial and domestic wastewater, urea can decompose into hazardous species such as nitrate and ammonia [83]. Hybrid water electrolysis that couples the urea oxidation reaction (UOR) with the HER therefore provides a dual benefit: hydrogen production and wastewater remediation. The calculated E^0 for urea formation from nitrogen, carbon dioxide, and water (Equation 10) is 0.76 V_{SHE} , yielding a meaningful reduction in electrical energy input compared to the OER [84]. This combination of environmental and economic advantages positions urea as an attractive alternative anodic substrate for green hydrogen production.

2.3.1 | Electrolysis Products

The six-electron UOR (Equation 10) yields exclusively non-toxic gaseous products when properly controlled, making it environmentally appealing, provided that CO_2 is captured and overoxidation to NO_x^- species is avoided [152]. Although the mechanism remains under debate, several pathways have been proposed depending on the electrocatalyst. These have been comprehensively reviewed elsewhere [153], so here, we highlight only their implications for catalyst design. In the adsorbate evolution mechanism, CO_2 desorption is often rate-limiting and can lead to surface poisoning [154]. A related coupled chemical-electrochemical pathway involves dehydrogenation of surface-adsorbed NH_2 species along with CO_2 desorption as the rate-determining step [155]. Faster kinetics is associated with lattice oxygen-mediated pathways, though these require M(IV) sites as active centers [156]. Finally, on some catalysts, parasitic routes leading to NO_x^- formation can occur due to preferential C–N cleavage and OH^- attack [152, 157]. Collectively, these competing mechanisms present significant challenges to catalyst activity and stability, constraining the applicability of the UOR in hybrid electrolysis systems.

2.3.2 | Noble Metal Catalysts

To navigate the mechanistic complexity of the UOR, early studies turned to noble metals because of their strong oxidizing capability. The first report of electrochemical urea oxidation, by Yao and colleagues, observed oxidation at 0.80 V_{RHE} using a polycrystalline Pt electrode, though the product distribution was only inferred [158]. Subsequent on-line mass spectrometry revealed that Pt predominantly produces not only CO_2 and N_2 but also small amounts of undesired NO_x^- [159], providing early evidence that overoxidation can occur. The formation of nitrites and related species has since become a central concern, given that they compromise the environmental advantages of the UOR.

To modulate the overly strong oxidizing behavior of noble metals and reduce cost, many recently reported strategies use

them only sparingly as promoters within 3d metal-based catalyst frameworks. For example, Ru-doped Co₂P nanoparticles supported on N-doped carbon nanosheets atop Ni foam (Ru-Co₂P/N-C/NF) achieved the lowest potential (1.30 V_{RHE}) required to reach 10 mA cm⁻² among a series of Ni foam-supported transition-metal catalysts (Figure 8A) [160]. Ru incorporation improved the charge-transfer kinetics of the Co₂P phase, whereas the nanosheet architecture increased the surface area and the number of exposed active sites.

Similarly, Zheng and colleagues demonstrated that a 2D/2D NiO-anchored Ru-Co heterostructure could catalyze the UOR, achieving 10 mA cm⁻² at 1.29 V_{RHE} before the onset of Ni(II)/Ni(III/IV) oxidation, as confirmed by operando Raman spectroscopy [161]. DFT-calculated projected density of states revealed strong Co 3d, Ni 3d, Ru 4d, and O 2p orbital overlap, which was proposed to enhance charge-transfer capability and thereby improve UOR performance relative to earlier systems (Figure 8B). The potential-determining step was identified as the deprotonation of adsorbed CONHN to form adsorbed CON₂ (Figure 8C).

A further illustration of efficient noble metal utilization is provided by NiO nanosheets decorated with Rh nanocrystals, where Rh sites selectively facilitated the oxidation of Ni(II) to catalytically active Ni(III/IV). This catalyst reached 616 mA mg⁻¹ at 1.55 V_{RHE}, an 11.5-fold improvement over bare NiO [162].

Together, these studies demonstrate that small amounts of noble metals can significantly lower operating potentials and improve reaction kinetics for urea-assisted hybrid water electrolysis. Nevertheless, their use should remain judicious to

avoid overoxidation pathways and to retain economic feasibility.

2.3.3 | Non-Noble Metal Catalysts

As with the previous substrates, recent efforts have increasingly prioritized electrocatalysts composed of earth-abundant elements as cost-effective alternatives to noble metals. Foundational work by Boggs and colleagues established that the Ni(II)/Ni(III/IV) redox transition is once again essential for catalyzing the UOR in alkaline media [64]. They also demonstrated that NiOOH-modified Ni electrodes supported on a range of Ni and Ti substrates deliver higher urea-oxidation current densities than their unmodified counterparts. These observations underscore the recurring importance of interface and support engineering as a strategy to enhance UOR activity.

Supporting this view, one representative example involves NiO nanosheets vertically grown on CuO nanowires, which achieved 100 mA cm⁻² at 1.39 V_{RHE}. The high activity arises from efficient charge transfer from CuO to NiO, whereas DFT calculations showed that the system has low CO₂ adsorption energy, thereby reducing susceptibility to catalyst poisoning [163]. DFT studies on NdNiO₃-NiO heterointerfaces further attributed their high UOR activity to an optimal balance of strong urea adsorption and weak CO₂ desorption energies (Figure 9C) [164]. Together, these results suggest that CO₂ binding may serve as a useful activity descriptor for screening prospective UOR electrocatalysts.

Heterojunction engineering has also been investigated as a means to enhance UOR performance, particularly through the development of Mott-Schottky catalysts composed of metal-

FIGURE 8 | (A) Linear sweep voltammetry curves of nickel foam (NF) with and without supporting various catalysts in 1.00 M KOH and 0.50 M urea at a scan rate of 5 mV s⁻¹. Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2020, published by Elsevier B.V [160]. (B) UOR activity comparison between 2D/2D NiO-anchored Ru-Co and previous catalysts at 10.00 mA cm⁻². Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2023, published by Wiley-VCH GmbH [161]. (C) DFT-calculated Gibbs energy diagram for the UOR on the same catalyst. Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2023, published by Wiley-VCH GmbH [161].

FIGURE 9 | (A) Illustration of the UOR process (top) and proposed reaction mechanism on a CoS_2 - MoS_2 Schottky catalyst (bottom). Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2018, published by Wiley [165]. (B) Cyclic voltammograms of LaNiO_3 perovskite supported on Vulcan carbon in the presence of 0.33 M urea and varying concentrations of KOH at a scan rate of 10 mV s^{-1} . Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2016, published by American Chemical Society [154]. (C) Comparison of DFT-calculated urea and CO_2 adsorption energies on hydroxylated NiO, NdNiO_3 , and the NdNiO_3 -NiO heterointerface. Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2025, published by Elsevier B. V [164].

semiconductor junctions whose differing Fermi levels drive spontaneous electron flow across the interface. The resulting electron-rich and electron-deficient regions align well with the dual donor-acceptor nature of urea, making such architectures attractive candidates (Figure 9A, top). This concept was validated for a $\text{CoS}_2/\text{MoS}_2$ heterointerface, which reached 10 mA cm^{-2} at $1.29 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$, with DFT calculations confirming favorable interfacial adsorption of urea [165]. Related systems such as $\text{CoMn}/\text{CoMn}_2\text{O}_4$ have also been examined but show somewhat reduced activity (10 mA cm^{-2} at $1.32 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$) [166]. These studies indicate clear potential for further optimization of Mott-Schottky catalysts to achieve high current densities at even lower operating potentials.

Returning to Ni-based catalysts, their performance can be enhanced through doping or alloying to facilitate the Ni(II)/Ni(III/IV) transition at lower potentials. Forslund and co-workers, for example, reported a LaNiO_3 perovskite supported on Vulcan carbon (XC-72) with an onset potential of ca. $1.39 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$, around 100 mV lower than unmodified Ni electrodes. They also

observed that increasing the electrolyte pH lowers the onset potential for urea oxidation (Figure 9B) [154]. In another study, a multilayer boron-nickel catalyst enabled urea-assisted electrolysis at $1.40 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$ and 100 mA cm^{-2} , outperforming NiO by a factor of 7.5 in current density at $1.45 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$. This enhancement was attributed to BO_2^- -mediated promotion of Ni oxidation to the catalytically active NiOOH phase [167].

As with noble metal-based systems, care must be taken to ensure that Ni-based electrocatalysts prioritize oxidation to N_2 rather than hazardous nitrite or cyanate species. Overoxidation is favored when urea binds in a monodentate fashion through a single N atom; this can be mitigated through Cu doping [152] or by coating the catalyst with polyaniline [157], both of which help suppress undesired pathways.

2.3.4 | Reaction Optimization Principles

Given the mechanistic complexity of the UOR and its sensitivity to catalyst structure and operating conditions, we outline

several research directions that could further advance its integration into hybrid water electrolysis. Noble metal-based catalysts should be used judiciously, as their strong oxidizing character can promote overoxidation to environmentally harmful NO_x^- species. When used, their role is best limited to that of promoters within predominantly $3d$ metal frameworks, where they can enhance charge-transfer kinetics without dominating the reaction pathway. Approaches such as sparse noble metal nanoparticle deposition or the construction of heterostructures offer effective routes to leverage their activity while maintaining low material cost and minimizing overoxidation risk.

Further cost reduction will require complete omission of noble metals, placing emphasis on improving earth-abundant systems, particularly Ni-based catalysts. Given its demonstrated promise, heterostructure engineering warrants continued and expanded investigation, both to accelerate electron transfer and to create interfacial environments that suppress unproductive adsorption modes. Complementary strategies such as alloying or doping can lower the onset potential for the formation of the catalytically active Ni(III/IV) species and simultaneously reduce the propensity for overoxidation to nitrites.

As with HMF oxidation, computational studies will be essential for moving beyond empirical catalyst development. Early evidence suggests that urea binding energy and CO_2 desorption energy may serve as meaningful catalytic activity descriptors, offering a foundation for mechanistic understanding and rational screening of new materials.

Overall, the UOR presents an attractive opportunity to couple wastewater remediation with green hydrogen production. Although urea itself has limited intrinsic value, its abundance in wastewater streams and relatively low oxidation potential make it a practical substitute for the OER. Nevertheless, key challenges remain, including CO_2 capture, suppression of overoxidation to nitrites, and enhanced charge-transfer kinetics for this demanding multielectron process. Addressing these limitations could pave the way for scalable hybrid HER-UOR systems capable of delivering environmental remediation and renewable energy generation in tandem.

2.4 | Methanol and Ethanol Oxidation

The final organic substrates examined in this review are the short-chain alcohols methanol and ethanol, which, unlike urea, can both be valorized upon electro-oxidation. Methanol can be produced sustainably via biomass fermentation [22], and its synthesis from biogas generated through anaerobic digestion of agricultural or industrial waste has gained recent attention (Figure 10A) [168]. The E^0 of methanol from CO_2 is $0.02 \text{ V}_{\text{SHE}}$ (Equation 11) [85], markedly lower than that of the OER, corresponding to an estimated 70% reduction in energy input relative to conventional water electrolysis [169]. These factors position methanol as a compelling alternative anodic substrate for hybrid HER-OOR systems.

Ethanol has likewise been explored as an oxidation substrate to support hydrogen production. It can be sourced renewably from biomass fermentation or via steam reforming of agricultural

FIGURE 10 | (A) Schematic of conversion of methanol and ethanol from biomass into OOR substrate. (B) Possible electrolytic reaction pathways for methanol and ethanol to marketable products or energy.

waste [110], and is significantly less toxic than methanol. Its E^0 from CO_2 is $0.09 \text{ V}_{\text{SHE}}$ (Equation 12) [85], slightly higher than methanol's, yet still well below the OER potential. Ethanol therefore remains an attractive candidate for hybrid electrolyzers that seek to pair hydrogen generation with value-added chemical synthesis.

2.4.1 | Electrolysis Products

The complete oxidation of methanol to CO_2 is well established in the context of direct methanol fuel cells [170], but increasing interest has shifted toward its partial electro-oxidation to formic acid (or formate) and formaldehyde due to their higher market value [66]. Methanol oxidation can proceed along two general pathways depending on the sequence and site of dehydrogenation [171]. Methanol is first oxidized to formaldehyde via a two-electron process, followed by oxidation to formate (four electrons), and ultimately to CO_2 (six electrons). An indirect pathway involving adsorbed CO is also possible, although this intermediate is a well-known catalyst poison and should be avoided.

As noted earlier for the GOR, formic acid is used in leather tanning and in direct formic acid fuel cells [92–94], and is roughly four times more economically valuable than methanol [172]. In a similar vein, formaldehyde serves as a precursor in resin production and as a laboratory preservative [173], further underscoring the incentive to steer toward these partial oxidation products.

Ethanol oxidation similarly yields both valuable intermediates and undesired overoxidation products. Partial oxidation produces acetic acid (or acetate), acetaldehyde, and ethyl acetate, whereas deeper oxidation leads to CO_2 formation analogous to methanol (Figure 10B). The reaction pathway mirrors that of methanol, with ethanol first oxidized to acetaldehyde (two electrons), then acetic acid (four electrons), and finally CO_2 (twelve electrons) [174]. Ethyl acetate can also form via esterification and oxidation of the in situ generated acetaldehyde with ethanol (four electrons) [175]. Given these competing pathways, selectivity for value-added products rather than CO_2 hinges on the catalysts' capacity to promote C–C bond scission and to avoid deactivation by adsorbed CO. These selectivity considerations gain further relevance, given the diverse applications of the targeted oxidation products. For example, acetaldehyde has broad industrial relevance as an intermediate in pharmaceutical, dye, and fragrances synthesis [176], whereas acetic acid is a major industrial feedstock and the principal component of vinegar [177]. Electrosynthesis of ethyl acetate has also emerged as a promising route, coupling hydrogen production with the formation of a solvent of appreciable market value under milder conditions than traditional thermocatalytic processes [75, 175]. These wide-ranging applications reinforce ethanol's status as a promising OOR candidate by highlighting the substantial economic value that selective electro-oxidation can unlock.

2.4.2 | Noble Metal Catalysts

Early studies of methanol and ethanol electro-oxidation frequently used noble metal catalysts, most notably Pt and Pd, owing to their strong alcohol oxidation activity. Initial reports

on methanol electro-oxidation used Pt anodes, producing formaldehyde in non-aqueous media and progressively higher formate concentrations as the water content was increased [178]. Subsequent aqueous-phase studies demonstrated that the Pt surface structure plays a defining role in both activity and selectivity. In particular, Pt(111) delivers the highest formic acid selectivity and the lowest onset potential ($0.40 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$), because hindered C–C bond cleavage suppresses deeper oxidation. In contrast, Pt(100) and Pt(110) facilitate C–C scission and therefore are more susceptible to CO poisoning [179].

Additional work has shown that preoxidation of Pt electrodes enhances current efficiency toward formaldehyde, whereas unmodified Pt favors formate formation [180]. This improvement requires higher cell potentials, demonstrating a clear trade-off between energy input and current efficiency. Figure 11C illustrates this comparison and highlights how surface oxidation state critically influences product distribution in methanol electro-oxidation.

Ethanol electro-oxidation on Pt was first reported in the 1980s [183], and, as with methanol, later studies highlight the strong influence of the catalytic surface structure on product distribution. Rizo and colleagues showed that Pt(111) promotes acetic acid formation at ca. $0.45 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$ because adsorbed acetate blocks OH^- adsorption and prevents further oxidation to CO_2 [184]. In contrast, Pt(100) favors acetaldehyde formation and allows its subsequent oxidation to CO_2 . This mechanistic divergence aligns with the findings of Giz and Camara [185], who identified two parallel pathways for acetic acid formation, including one that proceeds through a direct route that does not require acetaldehyde as an intermediate.

Pd has also been explored for ethanol oxidation due to its resistance to CO poisoning. As on Pt, different crystal facets yield distinct selectivity patterns. Pd(100) shows a lower onset potential for acetic acid formation ($0.37 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$) than Pd(111) ($0.41 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$), although DFT studies indicate that Pd(111), despite its slightly higher onset, provides superior selectivity toward acetate (Figure 11A) [181].

Further improvements in selectivity and activity have been achieved through alloying noble metals, which also increases atom economy and decreases manufacturing costs. Because methanol and ethanol share similar oxidation mechanisms, these alloying strategies are likely transferable across both substrates. For example, Pd–Sn catalysts with various compositions supported on carbon were evaluated for ethanol oxidation, with $\text{Pd}_{86}\text{Sn}_{14}$ identified as the optimal ratio. This catalyst delivered higher current densities and enhanced acetate formation relative to commercial Pd/C [186], with an onset potential of ca. $0.52 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$. DFT calculations suggested that alloying lowers thermodynamic dehydrogenation energetics compared to monometallic Pd.

In another case, an electrode consisting of Pd and Zn supported on N-doped carbon-coated ZnO nanorods operated at an onset potential of approximately $0.40 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$. This value is considerably lower than the ca. $0.60 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$ associated with standard Pd/C, and the catalyst sustained higher current densities across the $0.60\text{--}1.00 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$ window while maintaining strong selectivity toward acetate (Figure 11B) [182]. Cost-efficient Ru use was also demonstrated in Ru-anchored porous Pt_3Ni alloy electrodes, which selectively oxidized ethanol to acetate at $0.70 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$

FIGURE 11 | (A) Linear sweep voltammetry curve on a polycrystalline Pd/C electrocatalyst with 1.00 M KOH and 1.00 M ethanol at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹, with potential ranges for specified adsorption states on corresponding facets depicted. Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2021, published by American Chemical Society [181]. (B) Cyclic voltammetry curves comparing various Pd and Zn catalysts supported on N-doped carbon-coated ZnO nanorods to commercial Pd/C recorded in N₂-saturated 1.00 M KOH and 1.00 M ethanol at room temperature at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. Reproduced under the terms of the CC-BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). Copyright 2021, The Authors, published by Springer Nature [182]. (C) Comparison with the literature of current efficiency for methanol oxidation to formaldehyde on Pt and preoxidized Pt electrodes after 1 h in 8.00 M methanol and 0.50 M H₂SO₄ at different current densities, paired with HER. Reproduced under the terms of the CC-BY-NC-ND license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>). Copyright 2023, The authors, published by American Chemical Society [180].

(125 mA cm⁻²). DFT analysis indicated that Ru incorporation enhances OH adsorption and facilitates desorption of acetic acid, thereby promoting selective oxidation [187].

Collectively, these studies show that careful design and controlled use of noble metal catalysts, including facet engineering, alloying, and surface chemistry modification, can enable energy-efficient valorization of methanol and ethanol while limiting cost and improving selectivity.

2.4.3 | Non-Noble Metal Catalysts

As previously discussed, noble metal-free catalysts are among the most economically and environmentally attractive options for hybrid water electrolysis. Ni-based materials are used extensively because high-valent Ni(III/IV) species are effective in oxidizing alcohol functional groups. Consequently, catalyst activity is strongly influenced by the onset potential for Ni surface oxidation and by the degree to which interface engineering can enhance charge transfer and current densities.

For example, porous Ni electrodes have enabled ethanol-to-acetic-acid conversion at potentials approximately 200 mV lower than those required for the OER when operating at 50 mA cm⁻² (onset potential ca. 1.30 V_{RHE}, Figure 12B) [188]. Comparable behavior is observed for methanol: NiO nanosheet arrays on nickel foam catalyze methanol oxidation to formate at 1.53 V_{RHE} (100 mA cm⁻²), which is 280 mV lower than the OER potential required to reach the same current density [189].

Although effective, these potentials remain substantially higher than those achieved using noble metals. As a result, significant efforts have been devoted to lowering the onset potential of Ni-catalyzed methanol and ethanol electro-oxidation. Alloying and doping have proven especially useful in this regard. For instance, a NiMn LDH electrocatalyst enabled methanol-to-formate conversion at 1.41 V_{RHE} (100 mA cm⁻²) [190]. DFT calculations explained this improved activity over a similar NiFe LDH catalyst, with Mn raising the *d*-band center of Ni more effectively than Fe. This strengthens OH adsorption and decreases the thermodynamic energy required for Ni(III/IV)

FIGURE 12 | (A) Projected Density of States of Ni-3d electrons in NiMn LDH and NiFe LDH systems calculated using DFT, with the *d*-band center position marked. Reproduced under the terms of the CC-BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). Copyright 2023, The Authors, published by Springer Nature [190]. (B) Linear sweep voltammogram of a porous Ni anode in 1.00 M KOH in the presence and absence of 10 mM ethanol at a scan rate of 2 mV s⁻¹. Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2017, published by American Chemical Society [188]. (C) Linear sweep voltammetry curves comparing ethanol oxidation activity of CoNi hydroxide nanosheet electrodes to similar previously reported electrodes at pH 14 and a scan rate of 5 mV s⁻¹. Reproduced with permission: Copyright 2019, published by Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH and Co. KGaA, Weinheim [191].

formation. Similar improvements were observed when Cr was doped into Ni(OH)₂, which selectively oxidized methanol to formate at 1.45 V_{RHE} (50 mA cm⁻²). The enhancement was attributed to the formation of a hydrophobic interface that suppresses competitive water adsorption [192].

Parallel progress has been made for ethanol oxidation. CoNi hydroxide nanosheets, benefiting from synergistic Co–Ni interactions and heteroatom doping, show significantly enhanced activity and require only 1.39 V_{RHE} (10 mA cm⁻²) to produce acetate. This performance surpasses that of several previously reported electrocatalysts, reflecting a greater density of high-valent active sites (Figure 12C) [191]. Collectively, these examples underscore the importance of alloying and electronic structure tuning for optimizing methanol and ethanol oxidation in Ni-based hybrid HER–OOR systems.

2.4.4 | Reaction Optimization Principles

As with earlier substrates, noble metal catalysts offer low operating potentials for methanol and ethanol oxidation. However, their strong oxidizing capabilities require careful control of surface structure, alloy composition, or dopant incorporation to favor partial oxidation to valuable products rather than full oxidation to CO₂. In practice, these modification strategies also improve atom economy by reducing noble metal usage. Although alloying strategies have been more extensively explored for ethanol oxidation, we anticipate that similar improvements would apply to methanol due to the close parallels between the two reaction pathways.

For non-noble metal systems to become commercially competitive, substantial reductions in operating potentials are required. Ni-based catalysts already show encouraging selectivity toward value-added products, and their performance can be further enhanced through alloying, doping, and interface engineering to accelerate Ni(II) to Ni(III/IV) conversion and bolster charge transfer. Nevertheless, because Ni oxidation remains a fundamental requirement for catalysis, it may ultimately be necessary to explore non-Ni-based materials if the goal is to achieve onset potentials approaching those of noble metals. Catalysts effective for glycerol, HMF, or water oxidation provide a logical starting point, as these transformations share related mechanistic motifs.

Short-chain alcohol electro-oxidation therefore offers a promising route to replacing the OER in green hydrogen production, combining low operating potentials with high selectivity toward valuable chemicals. However, their parallel use in direct alcohol fuel cells should be considered when assessing feedstock availability for hybrid electrolysis applications (Figure 10B) [193]. Overall, these advances provide a strong platform for continued development of efficient methanol and ethanol oxidation catalysts tailored for integration into hybrid HER–OOR systems.

3 | Future Perspective

Despite the promise of hybrid water electrolysis as a next-generation platform for green hydrogen production, several critical challenges must be addressed before the OOR can effectively supplant the OER as the standard anodic process. Drawing on the literature and analysis presented in this review, we outline four strategic priorities to guide future innovation in this field.

3.1 | Rational Catalyst Design

Future research should prioritize catalyst designs that promote partial oxidation toward targeted, value-added products to maximize Faradaic efficiency and overall process profitability. Across substrates such as glycerol and HMF, product distributions are acutely sensitive to catalyst composition, surface structure, and electrolyte environment. As highlighted in Section 2.1.1, glycerol oxidation yields a broad spectrum of intermediates whose selectivity depends strongly on the applied potential and surface chemistry. Looking forward, integrating *in silico* screening to pre-evaluate catalyst properties before committing to resource-intensive experimentation will streamline development and reduce discovery costs.

Trialing OER-active catalysts for OOR processes may further accelerate progress. For instance, Prussian blue analogues have recently emerged as highly active OER electrocatalysts compared to non-Prussian blue-derived materials [194], making them strong candidates for OOR exploration. This strategy has already shown promise, as demonstrated in Section 2.2.3, where

OER-active NiFe LDH nanosheets performed exceptionally well for HMF oxidation.

However, despite being more thermodynamically favorable, many OORs show practical onset and operating potentials that exceed their E^0 values. This discrepancy is largely attributed to the formation of high-energy oxygenated intermediates, which, as in the OER, introduce significant kinetic barriers [23]. Overcoming these overpotentials will require a combination of advanced in situ spectroscopic techniques and computational modeling to identify, stabilize, or circumvent key intermediates and ultimately lower energy requirements while improving system efficiency.

3.2 | Industrially Relevant Durability and Performance Testing

Selectivity verified at low potentials or low current densities can be misleading under device-relevant operating conditions. As shown in Section 2.1.2 for glycerol oxidation on Pt–Au/Ni foam, C_3 selectivity decreases from 95% at 0.40 V_{RHE} to 62% at 1.60 V_{RHE} , despite achieving an impressive current density of 921 $mA\ cm^{-2}$. This is one of many examples illustrating how product distributions vary with potential, as in this case, whereas other studies have shown that electrolyte composition and catalyst surface structure can exert similar influences.

To address this gap, the community should benchmark performance under application-relevant conditions, combining a long-duration operation at realistic current densities with continuous tracking of Faradaic efficiency and product evolution. Establishment of standardized testing protocols and shared datasets aligned with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) [195] data principles will likewise be essential to ensuring reproducibility and facilitating meaningful cross-study comparisons.

3.3 | Reactor Engineering and Integration

The scalability of hybrid electrolysis will ultimately depend on translating laboratory-scale catalytic advances into full reactor systems capable of sustaining performance, selectivity, and efficiency under continuous operation. Many high-performance electrocatalysts are prone to surface poisoning (e.g., by CO), structural degradation, or corrosion, especially under harsh alkaline or acidic conditions. These degradation pathways compromise long-term performance and must be mitigated for industrial deployment.

Beyond the catalyst itself, system-level challenges such as membrane stability and product separation remain major barriers. In strongly alkaline media, many products form as salts, complicating downstream acidification and separation. Moreover, alkaline electrolytes like KOH require regeneration for stable operation, a process that is both energy- and cost-intensive. One innovative approach involves the use of cation exchange membranes that enable simultaneous KOH regeneration and acid recovery [196], although such integrated systems introduce additional complexity and capital costs relative to the established OER infrastructure.

Another key challenge is organic crossover through ion-exchange membranes, which can contaminate hydrogen streams, compromising purity and catalyst lifetimes. Strategies such as pulsed-potential electrolysis (see Section 2.1.4) can mitigate surface poisoning, but broader innovation in reactor design, membrane materials, and flow architecture will be required. Future progress will therefore depend on coupling catalyst optimization with advances in cell engineering and membrane durability to achieve stable, selective operation over extended timescales.

3.4 | Techno-Economic Viability

The economic analysis outlined in Section 2 provides an initial framework for assessing the profitability and value of different oxidation pathways. This analysis makes it clear that over-oxidation can significantly undermine economic viability and must therefore be minimized. At the same time, intrinsic product value is only one part of the equation; market scale and demand are equally essential. Even a highly profitable oxidation product offers limited practical benefit if its market capacity cannot support large-scale green hydrogen deployment.

Encouragingly, early techno-economic analyses demonstrate substantial benefits to hybrid systems. For example, Verma and colleagues estimated that replacing the OER with the GOR could reduce electricity consumption by up to 53%, yielding substantial cost savings [197]. Future research should continue integrating rigorous techno-economic analysis when identifying viable oxidation pathways and scaling emerging technologies.

These findings collectively highlight the transformative potential of hybrid electrolyzers and reinforce the need for continued innovation in catalyst design, membrane engineering, and system integration to fully realize the advantages of OOR-based hydrogen production.

4 | Conclusions

Over the past decade, replacement of water oxidation with organic oxidation reactions (OORs) has progressed from a conceptual idea to a rapidly expanding and impactful research frontier. When coupled with the hydrogen evolution reaction, the selective oxidation of substrates such as glycerol, HMF, urea, methanol, and ethanol offers a compelling strategy for green hydrogen production while simultaneously enabling the co-generation of value-added chemicals or supporting wastewater remediation. Beyond hydrogen generation, OORs can also be integrated with other electrochemical platforms, including CO_2 and nitrate reduction, further highlighting their versatility within renewable energy systems.

Recent advances in electrocatalyst development have enabled high current densities at operating voltages lower than those required for the OER. Noble metal catalysts often achieve low overpotentials but tend to promote complete oxidation, yielding lower value products. In contrast, non-noble metals such as Ni commonly show higher selectivity toward valuable partial oxidation products, albeit at somewhat higher voltages. Together, these trends highlight the promise of hybrid electrolyzers to improve energy efficiency, reduce greenhouse gas emissions,

and unlock new economic opportunities based on biomass- and waste-derived feedstocks. Achieving practical implementation, however, will require coordinated progress in catalyst design, reactor engineering, and techno-economic assessment.

In summary, hybrid water electrolysis has the capacity to reshape sustainable hydrogen production by pairing hydrogen generation with the valorization of abundant organic substrates. By integrating mechanistic understanding with economic insight, this review outlines a pathway for advancing OOR-based technologies toward the generation of green energy systems.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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